

**PRINCIPLES AND APPROACHES OF THE GEOLOGICAL AND GEOPHYSICAL STUDIES,
DEVELOPMENT AND PRODUCTION OF HC SHALE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10899563>

Abstract

The history of the study of bituminous shales dates back more than 200 years. But their active development and production began only in the 21st century. The article highlights the optimal concept of the development of HC shale based on the accumulated world experience and the author's forecast.

Keywords: Hydrocarbons, shale, fracking, horizontal wells, cyclic shale development, proppant, fractures, rehabilitation periods

The exploitation of the closed system deposits differs from the development of traditional reservoirs and traps, since there are no water aquifers in them and a reservoir pressure drop occurs due to the fact that the rate of production is many times higher than the rate of generation of new hydrocarbons portions. Wells in such formations are operated at depletion, since there is no possibility of oil displacement by water. The accumulated experience shows that the use of traditional methods of development makes it possible to extract only 3-5% of the STOIIP contained in HC shale [1].

Preparation of shale fields for development. The development of shale deposits requires an integrated approach, taking into account the type of reservoir and other features, composition and properties of oil and gas. Examples of such an analysis with the identification of the most prospective areas for the HC shale development is shown in Figure 1 [2]. Thus, the initial petrophysical study includes the determination of open porosity, effective porosity, reservoir water saturation, the relationship between Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, the relationship between acoustic impedance, brittleness and the total OM content.

Figure 1. Identification of the most prospective areas for HC shale development [2]

The relationship between geomechanical criteria shows a good matching of the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio: brittle rocks are in the area of low values of the Poisson's ratio and high values of the Young's modulus. The complexity of the geological structure of shales and their dynamic systems seriously complicates the production of shale hydrocarbons. Geomechanical analysis consists of calculating the dynamic Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratio, and the dynamic fragility index.

At the first stage, potential zones of HC accumulation are identified: seismic inversion, analysis of HC distribution, determination of the catagenesis gradation. The study of medium brittleness is carried out by using the acoustic impedance. Based on the results obtained, the most prospective areas are identified in terms of the reservoir qualitative characteristics and the presence of a certain type of hydrocarbon in it for horizontal drilling and fracking.

Seismic inversion. Seismic inversion is a good tool for predicting brittle and ductile rocks. The type of seismic inversion depends on the data set. The simultaneous inversion before summation is based on the calculation of the seismograms λ and μ . This type of seismograms can be used to calculate the velocities of longitudinal and transverse waves, which can be used to calculate the Poisson's ratio, Young's modulus and determine the value of the rock fragility [2-3].

Analysis of the OM maturity, determination of the catagenesis stage shale formations. Due to the simultaneous processes of HC generation and accumulation occur in the rock, the problem of accounting for the HC content was solved by combining of the catagenesis gradations prediction, elastic and geomechanical properties. The main oil formation zone and the main gas formation zone can be determined based on the values of the reflectivity of vitrinite, while the boundaries can be approximated and differ according to the type of kerogen.

Estimation of resources by the volumetric-genetic method (Potential Balance method [4]). The initial geological resources of the shale are can be calculated through the total volume of formation rocks, the percentage of TOC and the type of HC (catagenesis gradation), the rock density and the HC output out the rock (m^3/t):

$$Q = S \cdot h \cdot \rho \cdot \text{TOC} \cdot \text{HC}_{\text{yield}}, \quad [1, 4, 5, 8]$$

Where Q is HCIP; S — shale area, h — gross thickness of shale formation, $\rho_{\text{породы}}$ — shale density, TOC — total organic carbon, HC_{yield} — HC output out the rock (m^3/t).

Geomechanical analysis. Based on these criteria, potential zones of HC accumulation in the borehole space have been identified. Geomechanical analysis includes the calculation of the rock fragility. The term “brittleness” was introduced to define the relationship between the Poisson's ratio and Young's dynamic modulus for separating brittle and ductile rocks. The main assumption is that brittle rocks have low values of the Poisson's ratio and varying values from medium to high for the dynamic Young modulus [2-3].

Existing methods of the shale field development.

The average period of discovery, testing and implementation of a new technology for development and production takes 30 years. The following methods are provided for the development of HC shale fields:

1 – Natural flow development mode. According to experience, this mode ensures oil recovery during the development of the Bazhenov formation (RF - up to 5% on average) [1];

2 - Soda-surfactant-polymer effect on the formation, which is at the stage of experimental work [1];

3 - Fracking. This technology uses the natural energy of the deposit, the average maximum oil recovery is up to 10% [1];

4 – Thermal gas technology. This development is adapted only to the conditions of the Bazhenov formation, and allows to take advantage of the well-known Methods of oil recovery increasing. The predicted RF is up to 40% [1].

But the methods used to develop oil shales are technologically complex and economically inefficient. Suffice it to say that the gas RF at the world's largest Marcellus and Utica shale gas fields is assumed to be 0.1.

Production wells. Horizontal wells. Fracking.

The main way to develop shale formations is fracking – the creation of additional artificial (secondary) fractures in the area of brittle and compacted rocks, which ensures effective fluid movement to the well bore. At the moment, for the shale oil production, the most effective method is used - drilling horizontal wells (directional drilling) along with fracking, which allow covering significantly larger areas of the field compared to vertical wells.

At first (20-30 years ago), vertical wells were drilled for shale formations production, but due to their low productivity (rapid drop in flow rate), it was necessary to drill a large number of wells in a small area (Fig. 2).

But if the discovered reserves are located at some distance from an already drilled well, then it is more cost-effective to drill a horizontal side well bore to them than to move the rig to drill a new well (Fig. 3-4). Horizontal wells began to be drilled exclusively for the development of shale deposits, and then they began to be used for traditional reservoirs. The implementation of this technology does not depend on the type of rock, but on the specific situation and the profitability of its implementation. These are oil targets, the width and length of which are much greater than the thickness, but at the same time, the reserves of which fully pay off an expensive horizontal well.

The advantage of horizontal wells: 1 - multiple increasing of the drainage area for horizontal wells compared with vertical ones; 2 - the increment of the well contact area L/h for a horizon of smaller thickness is much greater than for a horizon of greater thickness; 3 - decreasing of reservoir permeability in the vertical direction significantly reduces the productivity of a vertical well; 4 - at low L/h the location of the well outside the center of the formation reduces its productivity, and productivity losses decrease with an increasing of the L/h ratio; 5 - to achieve the greatest reserves coverage (under equal conditions) the grid of horizontal wells is more sparse compared to the grid of vertical wells..

HC shales are extracted under conditions of artificial permeability creation (in most cases fracking) in horizontal wells (Fig. 5-6). The HC production level from a such deposits of the closed system drops by 75-100% during the first years, which does not allow the well to be operated naturally for a sufficiently long period of time.

Due to the fracking implementation, there has been a boom of shale gas/oil production. The essence of fracking technology is to create fractures inside the rock, allowing the release of HC accumulations. To do this, a vertical well is drilled (well pad), from which horizontal bores up to 2-3 km long diverge at (Fig. 5). Propant is pumped into the horizontal section - a mixture of sand, water and chemicals. Then a hydraulic shock is made inside the horizontal section. Hydraulic shock forms an interconnected system of fractures and

a void space from which HC can be pumped out. This method of shale gas extraction has already received industrial implementation in the United States.

Schlumberger's methodology for identifying the most prospective areas is based on combining the reservoir quality properties of and rock quality for potential drilling and fracking. This means that the place where the hydrocarbons are located and the place of well location and fracking must matching, but at the same time the technology has limitations for constructing a complex pore model, which does not take into account the OM voidness and the additional porosity formed as a result of the kerogen transformation.

Hydraulic fracturing technology provides higher productivity of producing wells. At the same time,

higher production rates are obtained with sufficiently low depressions. Fracking is used to increase the inflow by creating an additional or expanding an existing primary fracture system (Fig. 5). Fracking technology involves injecting a liquid mixture under high pressure, forming fractures in the formations through which oil or gas can pass to the well. A proppant agent is used to keep these fractures open. To produce a thousand cubic meters of gas, its need 2 m³ of water and 100 kg of sand. As a result of this development regime, the shale formation temporarily loses energy potential and requires additional pressure maintenance, for which is used repeated fracking. In Russia, fracking technology has been widely used since 1993 for underground gas storage.

Figure 2. High density of vertical wells within the shale oil field.

Figure 3. Horizontal single and multilateral wells.

Modern Shale Gas. A Primer, 2009

Figure 4. The construction of horizontal well (Modern Shal Gas, A. Primer, 2009).

Figure 5. The scheme of multi-stage fracking along a horizontal wellbore (R. Wasylshen & S. Fulton, 2012).

Figure 6. Formation of a fractured system after multi-stage fracking.

In this regard, knowledge about the fragility and plasticity of rocks will allow to assess the degree of necessary impact on the formation and determine the amount of water and proppant needed for fracking, as well as areas ineffective for fracking. This approach increases the profitability of projects by reducing the cost of production in the case of accurately determining of brittle and compacted rocks areas. Based on the use of indicators of fragility and plasticity of shale formations, it is possible to predict the spatial position of fractures and stress anisotropy at a qualitative and quantitative level, as well as an assessment of the need for water and proppant volumes. Specific volumes are obtained after integrating the data into the model.

Multi-stage fracking (MSF) along a horizontal wellbore. MSF – sequential fracking of a low-permeability formation in the well and the formation of fractures in several sections of the well is a high-tech innovative development of underground space by horizontal well boreholes of considerable length and coverage area (Fig. 6). So the HC output can be several times greater due to greater coverage, than in vertical wells without fracking.

The MSF is carried out in order to maintain the required size of fractures, and, accordingly, the well flow rate. It allows several full-fledged fracking operations to be carried out in one drilled horizontal well, which ensures maximum coverage of previously undrained zones by production, and the flow is intensified. The ballsiding-sleeve system is usually used (effects on the formation by continuously moving sliding multistage fracking). From six to eight horizontal wells drilled only within one cluster well can provide access to the same volume of the reservoir as sixteen vertical wells. The use of multi-lateral wells cluster can also significantly reduce the total number of well pads, necessary access roads, pipeline lines and necessary production equipment, as well as minimizing the concern of local fauna representatives, human and overall environmental impact.

The MSF technology makes it possible to introduce previously unprofitable reserves into development and increase not only the production rate, but also the RF. The stressed state of the rocks is confirmed by

buckling and fracturing of the core. Consequently, it is possible to release the energy of the rock by fracking impact and trigger the mechanism of fracturing in the near-well space by directional discharge of the formation in combination with fracking with a large drained area artificially created in the rock, an extensive system of fractures, which will perform the functions of a reservoir. Today, MSF is usually used in combination with other technologies (types of completion) to increase oil RF (with an open hole, with cementing, with microseismic monitoring, small-sized liner, with chemical deviation, with double packer, with proppant filling) (P.I. Kryukov, R.A. Himaletdinov S.A., R.G. Shaikamalov, A.N. Govzich, A.V. Bilinchuk, I.G. Fayzullin, Barletdinov S.A., Barkhatov E. A., A.M. Shurupov, P.N. Verkhovtsev, Yelesin M.V., Islamgaliev R.F.).

The technology of MSF has made it possible to make oil production from tight and shale reservoirs in North America economically efficient. This technology is becoming cheaper, mainly due to a decrease in the number of fracking stages. At the same time, there is an increase of oil production during the entire horizontal well working cycle.

One alternative (but more expensive) technology is anhydrous proppant fracking, in which liquefied proppant is pumped into the well under pressure as a gel.

Currently, 3 main types of fracking are widespread (Figure 7):

Slickwater is a traditional fracking method where water with acrylamide polymers is used as a reagent.

Hybrid is a traditional fracking, which uses a special method based on gel agents that reduce the friction of proppant transporting in the fracking fractures

Highway - fracking method with the creation of open channels

Innovative technologies of thermal gas impact have been developed to solve the problem of increasing RF of the Bazhenov formation reservoirs. With thermal production methods, the rock is heated to a high temperature, and the liquid obtained during distillation is

separated for further processing or with the help of injection wells, the permeability of the reservoir is increased and a mixture similar to traditional oil is pushed

to the surface, which does not require any additional processing before being sent to the refinery (an example is the Green River formation) (Fig.8-9).

Figure 7. Comparison of different types of fracking using for the Eagle Ford formation wells

Figure 8. The technology of the steam gravity drainage (SAGD)

Figure 9. The mechanism of thermal gas effect on the formation for the conditions of a low-permeability reservoir of the Bazhenov formation (A.S. Ushakova, V. V. Zatsepin, A. A. Kudryashov, P. P. Povzhik).

In Russia, the prospects for the development of an increasing share of hard-to-recover reserves are associated with the innovative of field production methods

based on the integration of thermal and gas methods of oil recovery increasing. The method of thermal gas impact in light oil fields was developed based on thermal

and gas methods of increasing oil recovery and oil production intensification.

For the first time, the thermal gas technology for air injection and the use of the energy potential of the formation for the in-situ transformation of the injected air into an effective displacing agent was proposed in 1971. The method is based on the injection of air and water into the formation and the transformation into effective displacing agents due to in-situ oxidative processes, a highly efficient gas agent containing nitrogen, carbon dioxide and wide fraction of light hydrocarbons is produced. The reservoir temperature is maintained at 65-70 °C with simultaneous injection of water and air.

A special feature of the thermal gas method is the use of natural reservoir energy, increased reservoir temperature for the spontaneous initiation of intra-reservoir oxidative processes and the formation of a highly effective displacing agent, the possibility of active spontaneous oxidative processes at lower temperatures, since real formations contain catalysts (CuO, MnO₂, Cr₂O₃, NiO, etc.), the maximum possible extraction of light oil from drained mainly of macro-fractured rocks due to the formed effective mixing agent, involvement in the development of kerogen-containing zones and HC extraction by thermal cracking and pyrolysis.

The method of thermal gas impact, despite the fact that it is based on physical and chemical processes similar to those that underlie thermal and gas methods, including the method of in-situ combustion, is based on fundamentally new physical foundations. In-situ oxidative processes ensure the in-situ transformation of the air injected into an effective, oil-miscible, displacing agent. The high temperature level formed in the drained zones (up to 350 °C), along with high reservoir pressure (over 20-25 MPa), ensures high efficiency of oil displacement by water pumped into the reservoir along with air. As a result, the areas covered by the oil displacement process, the mixing gas agent and hot water can provide almost complete displacement of the reservoir oil contained in these zones.

The injection of the water-air mixture ensures the creation of a thermal rim in the drained zone, the speed of movement and the temperature level of which must be regulated by the value of the water-air ratio.

It should be noted that this method will not be absolutely effective for shales with low permeability (Eagle Ford, Pimienta, Vaca Muerte, Domanic formations) and the presence of swelling clays, which, under the thermal gas impact, can significantly worsen the communication of natural and fracking fractures.

The method of thermal and gas methods integrating to increase oil recovery and intensify oil production. This method of thermal gas impact was developed at the junction of thermal (including the method of in-situ combustion) and gas methods of increasing oil recovery and intensification of oil production (Boxerman A.A., Greifer V.I., Kokorev V.I., Chubanov O.V., Korzhubaev A.G. Sonich V.P., Baturin Yu.E. Gorenje, Malyshev A.G., Zaripov O.G., Shemetillo V.G. Ignatova K.P., Malyukov V.P., Malyukov V.P.). The method involves pumping air and water into the reservoir. The high reservoir temperatures of the Bazhenov formation ensure the in-situ generation of a highly efficient displacing gas agent containing nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and light fractions of oil.

The method also allows the involvement of non-drained zones in the production by warming them up from the drained zones. The main method advantage is a significant reduction of the gas factor in producing wells in comparison with the use of air. The use of oxygen-enriched air makes it possible to solve a number of problems associated with the injection of working agents (for example, low reservoir pick-up rate and high formation heterogeneity).

Steam and gas impact. The steam-thermal wells processing (STWP) is associated with the heating of a limited reservoir area, compared with the drainage area (10-20 meters), by pumping steam or steam gas. The process contributes to a multiple decrease of oil viscosity, thermal expansion of the formation pore space and reservoir fluids, activation of the dissolved gas mode, an increase of reservoir pressure, a decrease of interfacial tension, adsorption of active oil components and, in general, a multiple increase of well flow rates. Hot water, steam of various quality, a mixture of steam and gas, steam with additives of chemical reagents, etc are a heat carriers of STWP.

Thermal impact of the formation with a steam-gas mixture using steam and gas generators (on monofuel), where diesel fuel, kerosene, distillate or natural gas are used as fuel, is one of the prospective production methods. The STWP can be used in combination with other methods of thermal impact, as well as an independent method of production. The composition of the steam-gas mixture, along with steam and droplet liquid, includes nitrogen gas. Such a components combination of the displacing agent has a complex effect on oil reservoir: *thermal* — heat exchange between the reservoir, including saturating fluids, and *gas dynamic* — gaseous nitrogen as a non-condensing component contributes to an increase of reservoir pressure and provides gas-liquid displacement, primarily due to an increase of pressure drop and the formation of a significant gas zone around the "injection-producing" well and displacement of trapped oil from fractures and small pores. The technology of producing steam gas at the downhole by burning monofuel provides for the combustion of HC liquid fuel in an oxidizer (air) environment. A single-phase cold aqueous solution of oxidizer and fuel is pumped into the well, injected from the surface via tubing by conventional pumping units and burned at the downhole in the combustion chamber to form steam and nitrogen gas. The interaction of oxygen with oil and kerogen initiates spontaneous oxidative processes in the formation with the heat release transferred to the area of the combustion front by gases and water. The kerogen contained in the deposit is subjected to pyrolysis and cracking, which increases the yield of hydrocarbons from the reservoir. The water injected with air turns into saturated steam with a temperature of up to 300-350 °C, which leads to an increase of pressure, an increase of fracturing, and, accordingly, the drainage zone. This technology makes it possible to increase the oil RF of the Bazhenov formation from 3-5% (achieved using traditional methods of development of the natural mode) to 30%.

Thermal gas impact (TGI) is a technology designed to involve non-traditional hydrocarbon resources of the Bazhenov formation. During the implementation of intra-horizon oxidative processes for the

Bazhenov formation, kerogen is used as fuel, which significantly reduces the cost of light oil for oxidation and combustion processes.

Oil is displaced from the reservoir directly by the thermal front, gaseous oxidation products, hot water and steam. The degree of significance of each displacement mechanism may be different. Currently, different terms are used to refer to technologies that have already been developed or are being developed based on injection of an oxygen-containing mixture into the reservoir, for example, thermal gas impact, intra-horizon combustion (IHC) and its modifications, high-pressure air injection, foamed oxygen injection, directed air injection technology (DAIT)

There are a number of features of the TGI determined by the geological and physical parameters of the Bazhenov formation. Thus, the TGI technology provides for the use of the advantages of methods developed for the production of light and heavy oil deposits, by taking into account the peculiarities of intra-reservoir processes while injecting an oxygen-containing mixture - this is the reaction of hydrocarbons with oxygen, along with the formation of aldehydes, alcohols, ketones and hydro admixtures and the thermal energy releasing.

In the process of in-situ combustion, the combustion front acts as a "bulldozer", displacing oil in front of it, which has not been extracted due to the other oil displacement methods. As a result, a mixture of gases, containing mainly carbon dioxide and nitrogen, displaces oil from the reservoir to the producing wells. The initial stage of the implementation of the technology of injection of an oxygen-containing mixture into the reservoir is associated with an increase of reservoir pressure and temperature. It has been revealed that high-pressure air injection should be considered as a joint process of thermal and gas impact, the thermal front has the ability to displace residual oil after gas impact.

Along with an increasing of temperature for all types of petroleum-containing rocks, an increase of porosity and permeability, initial flow rate, and accumulated production is noted [11, 12]. In this regard, it should be noted that some experimental studies have shown that an increase of the temperature of the microvoid space (matrix) makes it possible to extract up to 70-80% of the originally contained light oil and convert part of the solid kerogen into liquid and gaseous HC.

The generated thermal energy, along with hydroelectric action, has a decisive effect on the heating of adjacent non-drained areas of the formation and the extraction of light oil and HC gases due to the formation of conditions for the hydrocarbon accumulations generation (conversion of kerogen into light oil) and fractures.

In the USA, due to the use of thermal gas impact, 148 Ktons of oil were produced in 2003, 645 Ktons in 2005, 774 Ktons in 2006, 971 Ktons in 2008, 964 Ktons in 2010 [13].

In Russia, the technology of thermal gas impact has been implemented for the Bazhenov formation (Galyanovsky and Sredne-Nazymsky fields). For the development of unconventional reservoirs of the Bazhenov formation, this method is the most effective and expedient, both technologically and economically.

Other thermal methods.

The pyrolysis method is used for a deeper reservoir. This method involves increasing the reservoir temperature to 800 °C. It belongs to the thermal processing of oil shale and is used in the oil shale processing industry.

The hydrogenation method. In this case, hydrogen is attached to an organic compound. The reaction proceeds at a temperature of 400 °C using some kind of catalyst (copper, nickel, platinum).

The Shell ICP (Shell) method. The process is based on the gradual heating of isolated shale formations. The process of field development according to the ICP project is built as follows: at the first stage, the field is prepared for production, then "freezing walls" are installed along the contour. After installing the "freezing walls", producing wells are drilled, but first, not oil, but water flows through them, that is, the formation is maximally dehydrated. Then "heating wells" with heat pumps are drilled. Normally, 2-4 years pass from the moment the pumps are installed to the start of production. Due to the heating of shale formations to a temperature of 200 °C, the in-situ distillation of oil begins, after which light HC (usually diesel or jet fuel) are fed into injection wells. This makes it possible to separate light fractions from heavy fractions and supply a mixture of low-boiling hydrocarbons, that is, unstable gas condensate and associated petroleum gases, to the production wells wellheads.

Other modifications of thermal methods can also be cited: *Chevron in-situ process, Exxon Mobil Electofrac, AMSO EGL Technology, Alberta-Taciuk Process (ATP), EGL In-Situ Process* and others (Fig. 10-11).

Cyclic shale development (CSD) is proposed by the author [1] as a technology for long-term production of HC shale from isolated systems, which does not require special costs (Fig. 12).

The existing experience of the Maikop HC shales development (Batalpashin and Khadum formations) of the Central and Eastern Ciscaucasia shows that after a drop of pressure and a decrease of flow rates to a minimum, wells must be shutdown for a time (1-9 months) sufficient to restore reservoir pressure (5-Vorobyovskaya well). After wells shutdown to restore and compensate reservoir pressure in a self-regulating reservoir due to the processes of continuous active HC generation, oil flow rates are restored (sometimes close to the initial ones).

Such dynamics of oil production is confirmed by the long-term (for more than 30 years) development of a number of vertical wells from the Eagle Ford shale formation (Texas) (Fig. 13) [5-8]. The horizontal well completions (1000-2000 m) maximize the drainage area.

In similar fields of Bazhenov shale formation of Western Siberia, after a sharp drop of the HC production rate, wells are temporarily shut down (Fig. 14-15). And the more significant the pressure dropping, than more significant the processes of additional hydrocarbons generation, the thermal expansion of which partially extinguishes the process of reducing reservoir pressure and oil flow rate and accelerates the processes of deposit expansion in the fluid fractures dead ends of layered rocks. During the wells shutdown, reservoir pressure is restored in a self-regulating reservoir due to

the processes of continuous active HC generation. As a result the oil flow rates are restored. Thus, there is a cyclical dynamics of changes in reservoir pressure and the intensity of oil and gas generation. The appearance

of additional hydrocarbon reserves is the cause of abnormal reservoir pressure (ARP) and expansion of the formation fracture system. [3, 7].

Figure 10. Some of the oil shale production technologies.

Figure 11. The freezing wall of the shell for shale oil production (Shell ICP Conversion Process).

Figure 12. A graph of the cyclic shale development (V.A. Bochkarev [1, 4, 5, 8])

Figure 13. A graph describing the results obtained by EOG. Recovery of well flow rates during periodic development and fracking (Malanichev A.G., 2018).

Figure 14. The schedule of periodic operation of well-114 of the Salymskoye field [9].

Figure 15. The forecast schedule of pressure stabilization and recovery while the study of wells by the isochronous method and the express method. I-VI - modes, $t_p = t_b$ - stabilization time (well operation); t_b - recovery time [9].

The estimation of the optimal number of cycles of reservoir pressure recovery and HC reserves replenishment is based on the calculation of the generation potential of shale formations and the calculation of production using decline curves for a period of months to 4-5 years.

During the production, the process of reservoir pressure drop significantly outstrips the process of its recovery. If oil production is stopped, the fluids generated in the isolated system of the formations (oil, gas, organogenic water) will gradually increase the reservoir pressure up to ARP again as the HC expands. Thus, the cyclicity of low and high intensity of oil generation processes is observed.

To restore the initial flow rate of oil/gas, the following methodological approach can be used, which can be represented as an equation: $(36+3)*N$, (1)

Where 36 are months of operation and 3 are well shutdowns, N is the number of cycles of HC deposits replenishment depending on the kerogen content (calculated by the Potential balance method) [1, 4].

The time period for wells shutdown for shale formation may be different. The proposed method of cyclic shale development has confirmed its viability and

relevance for the Eagle Ford shale formation (USA, Mexico). Thus, it takes 2.5-3 months to restore the initial oil flow rate of 350-400 BBL/day for the Eagle Ford formation (Figure 13).

Prolonged and intense disturbance of the reservoir system disrupts the natural balance, which leads to a rapid drop of reservoir pressure and a rapid decrease of flow rate. N.P. Zapivalov and I.P. Popov [13] noted that the threshold disturbance to the system can be estimated through reservoir depression, which, as detected for many HC fields should not exceed 5 MPa.

Compliance with the critical depression threshold (about 5 MPa), rehabilitation periods ("refueling") and gentle methods of increasing oil recovery are necessary conditions for long-term and effective development of oil and gas shale deposits due to the independent restoration of the natural system.

From the very beginning of the shale field development, it is necessary to ensure periodic geo-fluid dynamic monitoring and temporary production shutdowns in order to ensure the restoration of HC reserves by resuming the HC generation process. Each new development cycle should begin with repeated fracking to open remote fractures (Figure 16).

Figure 16. The principle scheme of cyclic shale development.

The proposed principle of cyclic shale development will significantly minimize the cost of drilling a large number of production wells, extend the life (operation) of existing wells and reduce the CAPEX in general. This approach allows to preserve the generation potential of the developed formations, provides the compliance with the critical depression threshold (about 5 MPa), the implementation of rehabilitation periods ("refueling" for 0.5-2.5 months) and gentle methods of increasing oil recovery due to the independent restoration of the natural system.

Due to cyclic shale development, it is possible to refuse to intensive fluid extraction technologies (forced production, which is exactly what is observed in most fields of the world) and be guided by the principle of "sparing" development, and the production of renewable natural resources should be based on a scientifically based approach on balance of HC generation volumes and adequate oil-and-gas flow rate.

Cyclic shale development will allow to achieve maximum IRR (>50%) and NPV along with the longest possible production period [1, 10].

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